

On the Generalization of Machine Learning for mmWave Beam Prediction

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Abstract—Owing to the crucial importance of the beam management (BM) procedure in millimeter-wave (mmWave) communication systems, machine learning (ML)-based beam prediction is currently being studied in the 3rd Generation Partnership Project (3GPP). The targets of these studies, in addition to reduction in reference signal (RS) overhead, latency, and power consumption, are to investigate low-complexity ML solutions that can cope up with wireless channel dynamism. Therefore, in this article, we investigate the aspect of ML model generalization and propose a low-complexity meta ensemble learning (MEL) design that facilitates efficient spatial domain beam prediction over different wireless channel conditions. Evaluation results over 3GPP specified channel models demonstrate that the proposed design can generalize well over different channel conditions and achieves a beam prediction accuracy of 93% and 81% over line-of-sight (LOS) and non-line-of-sight (NLOS) scenarios, respectively, with significantly lower computational complexity as compared to the state of the art.

Index Terms—Beam prediction, generalization, low-complexity, machine learning (ML), millimeter-wave (mmWave).

I. INTRODUCTION

Beamforming via large antenna arrays is indispensable to compensate for the severe pathloss caused by millimeter-wave (mmWave) frequencies [1]. However, to harvest the highest beamforming gain, both the base station (BS) and user equipment (UE) should collaborate in beam selection to identify the best beam pair that aligns well with the dominant path of the underlying channel. In fifth generation (5G) communication systems, this is achieved via a beam management (BM) procedure, where beamformed reference signals (RSs), known as synchronization sequence blocks (SSBs), are periodically transmitted from the BS to the UE. Subsequently, transmission of beam measurement reports containing the reference signal received power (RSRP) of downlink (DL) beams, from the UE to the BS, help identifying the best beam pair for subsequent data transmission [2].

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This exhaustive beam scan (EBS)-based BM procedure has two major drawbacks. First, periodic transmission of a large number of SSBs results in huge RS overhead, latency, and RS transmit power consumption. Second, beam switching for frequent beam measurements, quantization, and reporting consumes a large amount of UE power [3]. To overcome these limitations, a hierarchical beam scan (HBS) that covers the whole angular range with a fewer number of parent (wide) beams was considered [4]. However, its performance is sensitive to the parent beam selection, which due to imperfect patterns, reduced beamforming gain, and noise can result in an erroneous parent beam selection.

Machine learning (ML) is expected to trigger a paradigm shift in future wireless networks. One of the first concrete application of ML could be on BM, such as beam prediction in spatial and/or temporal domain, which is currently being investigated by the 3rd Generation Partnership Project (3GPP) for 5G-Advanced [5]. Consequently, ML-based beam prediction has attracted tremendous research interest. To this end, a straightforward approach for RS overhead reduction is to utilize contextual information of the UE location or other sensory information to train a deep neural network (DNN) for beam prediction [6], [7]. However, acquisition of such contextual information requires additional sensors and additional feedback overhead. To overcome this limitation, the study in [8] utilizes a convolutional neural network (CNN) to predict the best transmit beam based on the measurements obtained by probing a small number of parent beams. By extending the idea, a low-complexity design for beam prediction was proposed in [9]. However, due to the dependency on first-level parent beam scan, these solutions share the aforementioned limitations of traditional HBS.

On the other hand, focusing on RS overhead reduction several studies suggest to probe only a subset of candidate beam directions for partial scanning, where the obtained measurements are then exploited by a supervised DNN for identification of the best beam among all transmitted and non-transmitted beam directions [10]–[12]. In addition to the DNNs based on supervised training, several deep reinforcement learning (DRL) designs have also been proposed for beam prediction [13], [14]. However, to ensure iterative interaction between the BS and UE such methods require significant modification in existing systems that limits their practicality for 5G-Advanced communication networks.

Most of the aforementioned beam prediction solutions in [8]–[12] assume that the source (training) and target (test)

data samples are independent and identically distributed (IID). This assumption is often violated in the real world, where different wireless channel conditions cause a distribution shift between the training and test data samples [15]. Consequently, an ML model trained on specific environmental conditions may fail to generalize over other scenarios. Thus, to support beam prediction over different wireless channel scenarios, a BS or UE needs to train multiple scenario-specific ML models leading to a higher training, memory storage, and power consumption cost. Furthermore, such scenario-specific models require perfect scenario identification and model switching leading to a highly complex life cycle management (LCM) procedure which limits their practicality.

To this end, in this paper, we focus on the generalization of beam prediction under distribution shift caused by different channel conditions. Specifically, a sparsely sampled codebook design is proposed for RS overhead reduction resulting in reduced latency and power consumption. Further, by considering the line-of-sight (LOS) and non-line-of-sight (NLOS) channel conditions, we propose an ML-based meta ensemble learning (MEL) design for efficient beam prediction with enhanced generalization. To ensure the practicality of the proposed solution, the model training and testing dataset is collected using the 3GPP defined BM procedure and the performance is evaluated over 3GPP specified key performance indicators (KPIs).

II. SYSTEM MODEL

A. Antenna Array and Channel Model

We consider a DL mmWave massive multiple-input multiple-output (MIMO) communication system, where both the BS and UE utilize uniform planar arrays (UPAs) with $N_{\zeta,y}$ and $N_{\zeta,z}$ antenna elements on the y and z -axis, respectively. Further $N_{\zeta,y}N_{\zeta,z} = N_{\zeta}$ and $\zeta \in \{T, R\}$ represents the BS and UE, respectively. The antenna element spacing d_{ζ} for both the UPAs is $\frac{\lambda}{2}$, where λ denotes the wavelength. The array response vector $\mathbf{a}_{\zeta} \in \mathbb{C}^{N_{\zeta} \times 1}$ in the azimuth and elevation direction ϕ^{ζ} and θ^{ζ} , respectively, can be expressed as

$$\mathbf{a}_{\zeta}(\phi^{\zeta}, \theta^{\zeta}) = \mathbf{a}_{\zeta,y}(\phi^{\zeta}, \theta^{\zeta}) \otimes \mathbf{a}_{\zeta,z}(\theta^{\zeta}), \quad (1)$$

where \otimes is the Kronecker product and

$$\mathbf{a}_{\zeta,y}(\phi^{\zeta}, \theta^{\zeta}) = \frac{1}{\sqrt{N_{\zeta,y}}} \left[e^{j\pi(y'_c \sin \phi^{\zeta} \sin \theta^{\zeta})} \right]_{y'_c=0, \dots, N_{\zeta,y}-1}^T, \quad (2a)$$

$$\mathbf{a}_{\zeta,z}(\theta^{\zeta}) = \frac{1}{\sqrt{N_{\zeta,z}}} \left[e^{j\pi(z'_c \cos \theta^{\zeta})} \right]_{z'_c=0, \dots, N_{\zeta,z}-1}^T. \quad (2b)$$

Generally, mmWave massive MIMO channels are modeled as clustered delay line (CDL) [16]. Therefore, we consider a MIMO channel $\mathbf{H} \in \mathbb{C}^{N_R \times N_T}$ with a LOS path and C NLOS clusters with L paths per cluster, i.e.,

$$\mathbf{H} = \sqrt{\frac{N_T N_R K \Lambda}{K+1}} \alpha_{\text{LOS}} \mathbf{a}_R(\phi_{\text{LOS}}^R, \theta_{\text{LOS}}^R) \mathbf{a}_T^H(\phi_{\text{LOS}}^T, \theta_{\text{LOS}}^T) + \sqrt{\frac{N_T N_R \Lambda}{K+1}} \sum_{c=1}^C \alpha_c \mathbf{a}_R(\phi_c^R, \theta_c^R) \mathbf{a}_T^H(\phi_c^T, \theta_c^T). \quad (3)$$

Here, α_{LOS} is the complex gain of the LOS path, K is the Ricean factor, Λ indicates the pathloss, and $(\cdot)^H$ denotes the conjugate transpose. Further,

$$\alpha_c = \sqrt{\frac{1}{L}} \sum_{l=1}^L \chi_{c,l} e^{-j2\pi f_{\text{cen}} \tau_{c,l}}, \quad (4)$$

where the l -th path of the c -th cluster has a delay $\tau_{c,l}$ and complex path gain $\chi_{c,l}$, while f_{cen} is the central frequency.

B. Beam Steering and Measurement Model

We consider analog beamforming, where the BS transmit beamforming and UE receive combining vectors are selected from predefined codebooks $\mathcal{F} \triangleq \{\mathbf{f}_m \mid m = 1, 2, \dots, F\}$ and $\mathcal{W} \triangleq \{\mathbf{w}_n \mid n = 1, 2, \dots, W\}$, respectively. Further, the codebooks include $|\mathcal{F}| = F$ and $|\mathcal{W}| = W$ candidate beam directions that uniformly cover the whole range of angle-of-departures (AoDs) and angle-of-arrivals (AoAs), respectively. The codebooks are designed as

$$\mathbf{f}_m \in \mathcal{F} = \{\mathbf{a}_T(\bar{\phi}_1^T, \bar{\theta}_1^T), \dots, \mathbf{a}_T(\bar{\phi}_F^T, \bar{\theta}_F^T)\}, \quad (5a)$$

$$\mathbf{w}_n \in \mathcal{W} = \{\mathbf{a}_R(\bar{\phi}_1^R, \bar{\theta}_1^R), \dots, \mathbf{a}_R(\bar{\phi}_W^R, \bar{\theta}_W^R)\}, \quad (5b)$$

where $\bar{\phi}_m^T(\bar{\theta}_m^T)$ for the m -th transmit beam \mathbf{f}_m and $\bar{\phi}_n^R(\bar{\theta}_n^R)$ for the n -th receive beam \mathbf{w}_n are the quantized azimuth (elevation) AoDs and AoAs, respectively. These beamforming vectors, i.e., \mathbf{f}_m and \mathbf{w}_n are steering vectors in the direction of known point angles $(\bar{\phi}_m^T, \bar{\theta}_m^T)$ and $(\bar{\phi}_n^R, \bar{\theta}_n^R)$, respectively, and have the same mathematical form as in (1).

Assuming the DL transmission of unit power RS $x \in \mathbb{C}$ via the m -th beamforming vector, the received signal $y_{m,n} \in \mathbb{C}$ using n -th combining vector is

$$y_{m,n} = \sqrt{P_T} \mathbf{w}_n^H \mathbf{H} \mathbf{f}_m x + \mathbf{w}_n^H \boldsymbol{\eta}, \quad (6)$$

where P_T and $\boldsymbol{\eta} \in \mathbb{C}^{N_R \times 1}$ indicate the transmit power and additive white Gaussian noise (AWGN), respectively. Furthermore, the RSRP of the beam pair o is represented as $r_o \in \mathbb{R}$ and is obtained by averaging $y_{m,n} y_{m,n}^H$ over the measurement duration.

III. PROBLEM FORMULATION

To enable reliable communication and to achieve a high beamforming gain, the traditional BM procedure aims to identify the best beam pair o^* that maximizes the RSRP as

$$o^* = \underset{o \in \{1, 2, \dots, F \cdot W\}}{\text{argmax}} r_o. \quad (7)$$

Despite its conceptual simplicity, this EBS-based BM procedure requires $F \cdot W$ beam measurements as $\mathbf{r} = (r_o) \in \mathbb{R}^{F \cdot W \times 1}$. Consequently, it suffers from huge RS overhead, latency, and power consumption.

To ameliorate the limitations of traditional BM procedure, data-driven ML methods are exploited for efficient beam prediction. The beam prediction problem is usually articulated as a classification problem, where a DNN is trained to predict the best beam pair index \hat{o} based on the measurements obtained by probing a smaller subset of candidate beam

Fig. 1: Spatial correlation between the beam measurements over LOS (CDL-D) and NLOS (CDL-A) channels from [16] with 64 beams.

directions. More specifically, the DNN exploits the inherent spatial correlation between different beam measurements for efficient beam prediction [17]. The spatial correlation $\rho_{mm',n}$ between transmit beam m and m' as observed by receive beam n can be obtained as

$$\rho_{mm',n} = \mathbb{E}[y_{m,n}y_{m',n}^H] = \mathbb{E}[P\mathbf{w}_n^H \mathbf{H}\mathbf{f}_m x x^H \mathbf{f}_{m'}^H \mathbf{H}\mathbf{w}_n]. \quad (8)$$

Eq. (8) can be further decomposed into the spatial correlation over LOS path $\rho_{mm',n}^{\text{LOS}}$ and NLOS clusters $\rho_{mm',n}^{\text{C}}$ as given in (9a) and (9b) [18], respectively, where for $\xi \in \{\text{LOS}, \text{C}\}$

$$\begin{aligned} \beta_{1,y}^R &= \sin \bar{\theta}_n^R \sin \bar{\phi}_n^R - \sin \theta_\xi^R \sin \phi_\xi^R, & \beta_{1,z}^R &= \sin \bar{\theta}_n^R - \sin \theta_\xi^R, \\ \beta_{1,y}^T &= \sin \theta_\xi^T \sin \phi_\xi^T - \sin \bar{\theta}_m^T \sin \bar{\phi}_m^T, & \beta_{1,z}^T &= \sin \theta_\xi^T - \sin \bar{\theta}_m^T, \\ \beta_{2,y}^R &= \sin \theta_\xi^R \sin \phi_\xi^R - \sin \bar{\theta}_n^R \sin \bar{\phi}_n^R, & \beta_{2,z}^R &= \sin \theta_\xi^R - \sin \bar{\theta}_n^R, \\ \beta_{2,y}^T &= \sin \bar{\theta}_m^T \sin \bar{\phi}_m^T - \sin \theta_\xi^T \sin \phi_\xi^T, & \beta_{2,z}^T &= \sin \bar{\theta}_m^T - \sin \theta_\xi^T. \end{aligned} \quad (10)$$

Most of the existing works, such as [8], [10] rely on spatial correlation of beam measurements over the LOS path. However, it has been established that the LOS and NLOS data has different distributions and the NLOS data is usually more skewed than the LOS data [15]. Moreover, the complex gain of the NLOS path is usually much lower than that of the LOS counterpart and the misalignment between the directivity of the NLOS path $\mathbf{a}_\zeta(\phi_\zeta^\zeta, \theta_\zeta^\zeta)$ and quantized beam directions $\mathbf{a}_\zeta(\bar{\phi}^\zeta, \bar{\theta}^\zeta)$, as shown in (9) and (10), gives rise to a

Fig. 2: Selected beam directions for sparsely sampled codebooks.

severe channel power leakage¹ problem. This results in much lower spatial correlation over the NLOS scenario than that of its LOS counterpart as shown in Fig. 1. Consequently, ML models fail to generalize over NLOS scenarios that have much lower spatial correlation and different dataset distribution as compared to the LOS scenario [19].

IV. SOLUTION DESIGN

A. Sparsely Sampled Codebook Design

To reduce the beam measurement overhead, we design sparsely sampled codebooks $\tilde{\mathcal{F}} \subset \mathcal{F}$ with $|\tilde{\mathcal{F}}| = \tilde{F} = \frac{F}{d_T}$ and $\tilde{\mathcal{W}} \subset \mathcal{W}$ with $|\tilde{\mathcal{W}}| = \tilde{W} = \frac{W}{d_R}$. Here, d_ζ is a decimation factor that controls the size of sparsely sampled beam codebooks. To maximize the coverage in the whole angular domain, there should be a certain offset between the angles of selected beam directions in $\tilde{\mathcal{F}}$ and $\tilde{\mathcal{W}}$. Based on the spatial correlation, the selected beam directions for $F = 64$ and $d_T = 4$ are shown in Fig. 2. Here it can be observed that the selected beam directions in $\tilde{\mathcal{F}}$ are evenly distributed in the entire codebook \mathcal{F} . We now propose to probe these sparsely sampled codebooks for reduction in beam measurement overhead. Further, to deal with the nonlinear properties of the channel power leakage, we adopt a supervised ML approach that learns the spatial correlation between different beam measurements and predicts the quality of each beam pair between \mathcal{F} and \mathcal{W} , based on the RSRP measurements $\tilde{\mathbf{r}} \in \mathbb{R}^{\tilde{F} \cdot \tilde{W} \times 1}$ of sparsely sampled codebooks obtained as

$$\tilde{\mathbf{r}} = [\tilde{r}_{1,1}, \tilde{r}_{2,1}, \dots, \tilde{r}_{\tilde{F},1}, \dots, \tilde{r}_{\tilde{F},2}, \dots, \tilde{r}_{\tilde{F},\tilde{W}}]. \quad (11)$$

¹The channel angles do not necessarily lie in the direction of predefined quantized codebook angles, and a channel path whose angle is not equal to any of the predefined quantized angles will engender channel power leakage.

$$\rho_{mm',n}^{\text{LOS}} = \frac{P_T K \Lambda}{N_T N_R (K+1)} \mathbb{E}[|\alpha_{\text{LOS}}|^2] e^{\sum_{\kappa \in \{1,2\}} \sum_{\zeta \in \{T,R\}} \sum_{\delta \in \{y,z\}} \frac{-j\pi}{2} \beta_{\kappa,\delta}^{\zeta} (N_{\zeta,\delta} - 1)} \prod_{\kappa \in \{1,2\}} \prod_{\zeta \in \{T,R\}} \prod_{\delta \in \{y,z\}} \frac{\sin\left(\frac{\pi N_{\zeta,\delta} \beta_{\kappa,\delta}^{\zeta}}{2}\right)}{\sin\left(\frac{\pi \beta_{\kappa,\delta}^{\zeta}}{2}\right)} \quad (9a)$$

$$\rho_{mm',n}^{\text{C}} = \frac{P_T K \Lambda}{N_T N_R (K+1)} \prod_{\kappa \in \{1,2\}} \sum_{c=1}^C \mathbb{E}[|\alpha_c|^2] \left(e^{\sum_{\zeta \in \{T,R\}} \sum_{\delta \in \{y,z\}} \frac{-j\pi}{2} \beta_{\kappa,\delta}^{\zeta,c} (N_{\zeta,\delta} - 1)} \prod_{\zeta \in \{T,R\}} \prod_{\delta \in \{y,z\}} \frac{\sin\left(\frac{\pi N_{\zeta,\delta} \beta_{\kappa,\delta}^{\zeta,c}}{2}\right)}{\sin\left(\frac{\pi \beta_{\kappa,\delta}^{\zeta,c}}{2}\right)} \right) \quad (9b)$$

B. Meta Ensemble Learning for Enhanced Generalization

A straightforward approach to deal with LOS and NLOS channel conditions is to train their scenario-specific models. However, this requires perfect scenario identification and model switching resulting in a complex LCM procedure. Alternatively, one could think of training a single ML model for LOS and NLOS channels by combining their datasets. But due to the significant difference in the dataset distribution of these scenarios and due to the lower spatial correlation over NLOS channels, the ML model treats the NLOS input features as a noise. Consequently, the trained ML model suffers from high error variance that measures the sensitivity to fluctuations in the training dataset resulting in poor generalization performance [20].

To overcome these issues, we propose a simple MEL technique, where a meta learner combines the predictions from two or more ensemble members for enhanced generalization. Specifically, MEL involves building models using base algorithms, called level-0 models, and a meta learning algorithm, called meta model, to combine the predictions from the base models. By training multiple level-0 models on the combined dataset of LOS and NLOS scenarios and by averaging their predictions through the meta learner, we can reduce the error variance and can obtain a model that can generalize well over LOS and NLOS scenarios.

C. Meta Ensemble Learning Model Structure

The structure of the proposed MEL model consists of N_B base models and a meta model as illustrated in Fig. 3.

1) *Base Models*: Each base model consists of an input, an output, and two hidden layers.

Input Layer - The sparsely sampled codebooks designed in Section IV-A are initially probed and their RSRP measurements obtained by (11) and reported from the UE to the BS are used as an input to each base model. To reduce data skewness and to enhance data interpretability, the input is first normalized and then fed into the input layer.

Hidden Layers - To handle the nonlinear properties of the channel power leakage and to learn the spatial correlation between LOS and NLOS beam measurements, we introduce two fully-connected (FC) hidden layers consisting of $4\tilde{F}\tilde{W}$ and $8\tilde{F}\tilde{W}$ neurons, respectively. Furthermore, to enhance the nonlinear mapping capability, the output of each hidden layer is activated by a rectified linear unit (ReLU) activation layer.

Output Layer - To predict the quality of each beam pair, the last layer consists of $F \cdot W$ neurons. Finally, at the output of each base model $\varsigma \in \{1, 2, \dots, N_B\}$, the probability vector $\hat{\mathbf{p}}^\varsigma \in \mathbb{R}^{F \cdot W \times 1}$ is obtained by the softmax activation function

$$\hat{p}_o^\varsigma = \frac{e^{v_o^\varsigma}}{\sum_{\mu=1}^{F \cdot W} e^{v_\mu^\varsigma}}, \quad (12)$$

where $\mathbf{v}^\varsigma \in \mathbb{R}^{F \cdot W \times 1}$ represents the input to the softmax activation function.

Fig. 3: Structure of the proposed meta ensemble learning (MEL) model for beam prediction.

2) *Meta Model*: The predicted probabilities of all the base models are then provided as an input to the meta model, which yields the final output probability vector $\hat{\mathbf{p}} \in \mathbb{R}^{F \cdot W \times 1}$ as

$$\hat{\mathbf{p}} = \frac{1}{N_B} \sum_{\varsigma=1}^{N_B} \hat{\mathbf{p}}^\varsigma. \quad (13)$$

Since each base model is initialized with random weights, they result in different prediction probabilities. Consequently, by averaging the output probabilities of the base models it is expected that the error variance is reduced resulting in enhanced prediction accuracy and generalization [20].

D. Offline Training and Online Inference

For MEL model training, the input feature vector $\tilde{\mathbf{r}}$ is obtained by probing the sparsely sampled codebooks as discussed earlier in this section and the ground truth probability vector $\mathbf{p} \in \mathbb{R}^{F \cdot W \times 1}$ is obtained by (7) as

$$p_o = \begin{cases} 1, & o = o^*, \\ 0, & o \neq o^*. \end{cases} \quad (14)$$

The training dataset $\mathcal{D}_{\text{train}} = \{\tilde{\mathbf{r}}_i, \mathbf{p}_i\}_{i=1}^K$ consists of K input-output labeled samples. Consequently, the beam pair prediction problem is formulated as a multi-class classification problem, where each class corresponds to a candidate beam pair o . The loss function \mathcal{L}^ς for training of each base model ς is adopted as binary cross entropy (BCE), i.e.,

$$\mathcal{L}^\varsigma(\mathbf{p}_i, \hat{\mathbf{p}}_i) = -\frac{1}{F \cdot W} \sum_{o=1}^{F \cdot W} p_{i_o} \log_{10}(\hat{p}_{i_o}^\varsigma), \quad (15)$$

where corresponding to the i -th input vector, \hat{p}_{i_o} is the predicted probability of the o -th beam being the best.

Once all the base models are trained with sufficient training examples, they are switched to online inference mode. During inference, only the input feature vector $\tilde{\mathbf{r}}_j$ corresponding to the j -th testing instance is provided as an input. The MEL model then returns the predicted probability vector $\hat{\mathbf{p}}_j$. Finally, the best beam pair index is selected as

$$\hat{o} = \underset{o \in \{1, 2, \dots, F \cdot W\}}{\operatorname{argmax}} \hat{p}_{j_o}. \quad (16)$$

TABLE I: LIST OF SIMULATION PARAMETERS.

Parameters	Values
No. of BS antennas	N_T 64
No. of UE antennas	N_R 8
BS codebook size	(F, \hat{F}) (64, 16)
UE codebook size	(W, \hat{W}) (8, 2)
BS antenna gain	8 dBi
UE antenna gain	5 dBi
BS Transmit power	P_T 30 dBm
UE noise figure	N_F 6 dB
Center frequency	f_{cen} 28 GHz
Bandwidth	B 100 MHz
Sub-carrier spacing	120 kHz
Cell radius	200 m
Noise power	σ^2 $(-174 + 10\log_{10}B + N_F)$ dBm
Path loss at distance d	$(20\log_{10}d + 20\log_{10}f_{cen} - 147.56)$ dB

V. PERFORMANCE EVALUATION

This section evaluates the generalization behavior of the proposed MEL model over LOS and NLOS scenarios. All the default simulation parameters are listed in Table I. To generate LOS and NLOS scenarios, we consider 3GPP specified channel models from [16]. Specifically, the LOS and NLOS scenarios are generated with a delay spread of 100 ns and 500 ns, respectively. For evaluation of the MEL model, the combined dataset obtained via different channel profiles consists of 50,000 samples, where the training, validation, and testing data split is 70 %, 10 %, and 20 %, respectively. Further, the UE location is randomly drawn uniformly from the cell coverage area. The MEL model consists of N_B base learners, where each learner is trained for $n_{epoch} = 100$ epochs with a batch size of 64. The learning rate $l_\varepsilon = l_0 \cdot e^{-l_{dec} \cdot \varepsilon}$, where $l_0 = 10^{-2}$ is the initial learning rate that decays exponentially with the decaying factor $l_{dec} = 0.9$ and epoch ε . For performance evaluation in terms of overhead, the RS overhead reduction (in percentage) is defined as $1 - \frac{\hat{F} \cdot \hat{W}}{F \cdot W}$ and model complexity is evaluated in terms of number of trainable parameters and model size. Further, the distribution of the predicted top-1 and optimal beam pair's RSRP difference in dB is selected as a KPI for evaluation, where the optimal beam pair is obtained via traditional EBS [5]. Finally, the performance of the proposed MEL model is compared with [8], [10], where we have extended these transmit beam prediction works for beam pair prediction.

Fig. 4 showcases the impact of increasing N_B on beam prediction accuracy (at 0 dB RSRP difference) and model size. As can be noticed that by considering $N_B > 3$ yields only marginal gains in beam prediction accuracy, which comes at the cost of higher computational complexity. Therefore, to balance the model complexity and performance number of base models are selected as $N_B > 3$. Further, in terms of RS overhead reduction, the proposed approach only requires $\hat{F} \cdot \hat{W}$ beam measurements, i.e., an overhead reduction of around 94 % resulting in reduced latency and power consumption. Moreover, Table II demonstrates that the proposed MEL model structure results in lowest computational complexity that can be realized with simple hardware as compared to [8] and [10] and consequently benefits from lower power consumption.

 Fig. 4: Impact of number of base models N_B on beam prediction accuracy [%] with 0 dB RSRP difference and model size.

Fig. 5: Empirical distribution of the RSRP difference [dB] for NLOS scenario highlighting their dependency on scenario identification.

Fig. 5 evaluates the scenario-specific ML models from [8], [10] over the NLOS scenario. By assuming genie knowledge on the scenario identification, we can achieve an upper performance bound as shown in Fig. 5. However, false identification leads to significant performance degradation. Further, by considering only 10 % probability of false identification, which was achieved in [15], the performance of [8] and [10] degrades by around 9 percentage points for an RSRP difference of 0 dB. This performance degradation is due to the difference in spatial correlation of LOS and NLOS scenarios, as shown in Fig. 1. Furthermore, these solutions need a scenario identification mechanism that adds further complexity. Similar behavior was observed for the LOS scenario, which is not shown here due to space constraints.

Fig. 6a showcases the model generalization behavior over NLOS scenarios, where in addition to scenario-specific models, we evaluate the performance by training the models jointly over the combined dataset. It is to be noted that combined training eliminates the need of scenario

TABLE II: COMPUTATIONAL COMPLEXITY COMPARISON.

Model	No. of Trainable Parameters	Model Size (Mbits)
Proposed MEL	5.04×10^5	16.1
CNN from [8]	2.25×10^6	71.8
CNN from [10]	3.70×10^7	1,183.5

Fig. 6: Empirical distribution of the RSRP difference [dB]. Solid lines indicate the generalized solution with combined (LOS and NLOS) training. Dashed and Dashed-dotted lines represent the scenario-specific (NLOS or LOS) genie-aided and estimated solution, respectively.

identification as in this case only a single model is trained for LOS and NLOS scenarios. It can be observed that after training on the combined dataset, the solutions from [8], [10] suffer from higher model variance leading to overfitting and poor generalization. However, as it is shown in Fig. 6a, the proposed MEL design reduces the model variance and achieves higher generalization accuracy over the combined dataset. Specifically, for the 95-th percentile the MEL design outperforms the jointly trained model from [8], [10] by around 22 dB (not visible in Fig. 6a) and 10 dB, respectively, and achieves a comparable performance as the genie aided scenario-specific solution from [10].

Similar observations can be made from Fig. 6b, that evaluates the LOS scenario, where due to the stronger spatial correlation all the solutions achieve a comparable performance. Here, it is worth emphasizing that even with the significantly lower computational complexity of the MEL design, it achieves the performance of [10] with an RSRP difference of only around 0.07 dB for 95-th percentile. Consequently, the MEL design offers better generalization capabilities with significantly lower computational complexity which makes it suitable for practical applications.

VI. CONCLUSION

In this work, we have proposed an ML-based low-complexity MEL design for efficient spatial domain

beam prediction over LOS and NLOS channel environments. In particular, the proposed solution benefits from stronger spatial correlation over LOS channels, while over NLOS it reduces the error variance scenarios via a meta model resulting in improved performance over both considered scenarios. Simulations results demonstrate that the proposed solution not only reduces the RS overhead, latency, and power consumption but also offers enhanced generalization capabilities over various wireless channel conditions. These 3GPP compliant evaluations highlights the practicality of our proposed approach making it suitable for deployment in 5G-Advanced and beyond communication systems.

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